

Inflammatory Biomarkers and Hospital Stay in Acute Pancreatitis: The Role of CRP, RDW, MPV, and Albumin

Akut Pankreatitte İnflamatuvar Biyobelirteçler ve Hastanede Kalış Süresi: CRP, RDW, MPV ve Albüminin Rolü

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ABSTRACT

Aim: Acute pancreatitis is a common inflammatory condition with variable clinical presentation, ranging from mild, self-limiting episodes to severe disease requiring prolonged hospitalization. Early identification of patients at risk for severe disease is essential for improving outcomes. This study aimed to evaluate the association between routine inflammatory markers—C-reactive protein (CRP), mean platelet volume (MPV), red cell distribution width (RDW), and albumin—and the length of hospital stay in patients with acute pancreatitis.

Material and Method: This retrospective study included 164 patients diagnosed with acute pancreatitis between 2008 and 2013. Demographic and laboratory data, Ranson scores, and length of hospital stay were recorded. Patients were categorized by disease severity (Ranson score <3 or ≥ 3) and etiologic type (biliary vs. non-biliary). Laboratory cut-off values were determined based on literature data. Statistical analyses included t-test, Mann-Whitney U, chi-square, and Spearman correlation tests.

Results: The mean age was 58.4 ± 17.2 years, with a female predominance (65.2%). Biliary etiology was the most common (68.3%). Severe disease (Ranson score ≥ 3) was observed in 23.2% of patients and was associated with significantly higher CRP levels and longer hospital stays ($p < 0.05$). Patients with CRP > 150 mg/L or MPV ≥ 7.5 fL had significantly longer hospitalizations. Spearman analysis revealed a moderate positive correlation between CRP and hospital stay duration ($r = 0.458$, $p < 0.001$). RDW and albumin levels showed no significant association with hospital stay.

Conclusion: Among the evaluated markers, CRP was the most reliable predictor of prolonged hospital stay in acute pancreatitis. MPV may also provide limited prognostic information depending on the cut-off used. RDW and albumin were not found to be useful predictors in this context. These findings support the utility of CRP as a simple and accessible marker for early risk stratification in acute pancreatitis.

Keywords: Acute pancreatitis, C-reactive protein, mean platelet volume, red cell distribution width, albumin, hospital stay, inflammation markers

ÖZ

Giriş: Akut pankreatit, hafif ve kendiliğinden iyileşen ataklardan, uzun süreli hastane yatışı gerektiren şiddetli tablolara kadar değişen klinik seyir gösteren yaygın bir inflamatuvar hastalıktır. Şiddetli hastalık gelişme riski taşıyan hastaların erken dönemde tanınması, prognozun iyileştirilmesi açısından büyük önem taşır. Bu çalışmada, rutin inflamasyon belirteçlerinden C-reaktif protein (CRP), ortalama trombosit hacmi (MPV), eritrosit dağılım genişliği (RDW) ve albümin düzeylerinin, akut pankreatitli hastalardaki hastanede yatış süresi ile ilişkisi değerlendirildi.

Gereç ve Yöntem: Bu retrospektif çalışmaya, 2008–2013 yılları arasında akut pankreatit tanısı almış 164 hasta dahil edildi. Hastaların demografik ve laboratuvar verileri, Ranson skorları ve hastanede yatış süreleri kaydedildi. Hastalar hastalık şiddetine göre (Ranson skoru <3 veya ≥ 3) ve etiyojolojiye göre (bilyer veya non-bilyer) sınıflandırıldı. Laboratuvar kesim değerleri literatür verilerine göre belirlendi. İstatistiksel analizlerde t-testi, Mann-Whitney U, ki-kare ve Spearman korelasyon testleri kullanıldı.

Bulgular: Çalışma grubunun ortalama yaşı $58,4 \pm 17,2$ yıl olup, hastaların %65,2'si kadındı. En sık etiyojoloji bilyer nedenli (%68,3) idi. Hastaların %23,2'sinde ciddi hastalık (Ranson skoru ≥ 3) saptandı ve bu grup anlamlı derecede yüksek CRP düzeyleri ve daha uzun hastanede yatış süresi ile ilişkiydi ($p < 0,05$). CRP > 150 mg/L veya MPV $\geq 7,5$ fL olan hastalarda yatış süresi anlamlı şekilde daha uzundu. Spearman analizi, CRP ile yatış süresi arasında orta düzeyde pozitif korelasyon gösterdi ($r = 0,458$, $p < 0,001$). RDW ve albümin düzeylerinin yatış süresi ile anlamlı bir ilişkisi bulunmadı.

Sonuç: İncelenen belirteçler arasında CRP, akut pankreatitte uzamış hastane yatış süresinin en güvenilir öngörücüsü olarak saptandı. MPV, kullanılan kesim değerine bağlı olarak sınırlı prognostik bilgi sağlayabilir. RDW ve albümin ise bu açıdan yararlı belirteçler olarak değerlendirilmedi. Bulgular, CRP'nin akut pankreatitte erken risk sınıflandırması için basit ve erişilebilir bir gösterge olarak kullanılabileceğini desteklemektedir.

Anahtar Kelimeler: Akut pankreatit, C-reaktif protein, ortalama trombosit hacmi, eritrosit dağılım genişliği, albümin, hastane yatış süresi, inflamasyon belirteçleri

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INTRODUCTION

Acute pancreatitis is an inflammatory condition of the pancreas caused by premature activation of digestive enzymes within the gland (1). While most cases are mild and self-limited, a significant subset can develop severe complications, leading to prolonged hospitalization and increased mortality (2). Early identification of patients at risk for severe disease is therefore essential for timely management.

Although scoring systems such as Ranson, APACHE-II, and BISAP are widely used to assess disease severity, their complexity and reliance on multiple variables limit their practical utility in busy clinical settings (3-4). As a result, there is growing interest in using simpler, readily available laboratory markers to estimate disease severity and prognosis.

Routine hematological and biochemical parameters have shown potential in reflecting systemic inflammation. C-reactive protein (CRP) is a well-established acute-phase reactant that rises in response to tissue injury and inflammation for various diseases (5-6). Albumin is a negative acute-phase reactant, with reduced levels often reflecting both inflammation and poor nutritional status (7). Mean platelet volume (MPV), an indicator of platelet activation, tends to increase in systemic inflammatory states (8). Red cell distribution width (RDW) reflects the variability in erythrocyte size and may be elevated due to oxidative stress and inflammation (9).

These parameters have been investigated as prognostic indicators in various conditions such as sepsis, cardiovascular disease, and malignancy (10-12). However, their predictive value in acute pancreatitis, particularly in relation to hospital length of stay, is not fully established.

This study aims to evaluate the association between CRP, RDW, MPV, and albumin levels and the length of hospital stay in patients with acute pancreatitis. Hospital length of stay is a relevant clinical outcome as it reflects not only disease severity but also healthcare resource utilization, treatment response, and potential complications. Identifying simple markers that can reflect disease severity may help improve risk stratification and clinical decision-making.

MATERIAL AND METHOD

This retrospective study included 164 patients who were hospitalized with a diagnosis of acute pancreatitis between 2008 and 2013 at Dışkapı Yıldırım Beyazıt Training and Research Hospital. Demographic data, laboratory findings, hospitalization duration, and clinical scoring parameters were obtained from medical records.

The diagnosis of acute pancreatitis was based on the presence of at least two of the following criteria: (1) characteristic abdominal pain, (2) serum amylase and/or lipase levels at least three times the upper limit of normal, and (3) radiological findings consistent with acute pancreatitis on abdominal ultrasonography or computed tomography (13).

The etiology was classified into two groups: biliary and non-biliary. Patients with gallstones, biliary sludge, or markedly elevated cholestatic enzymes were categorized as biliary pancreatitis, while others were considered non-biliary. The severity of acute pancreatitis was assessed using the Ranson criteria at admission and at 48 hours (3). The severity of acute pancreatitis was assessed using the Ranson criteria. At the time of hospital admission, the following five parameters were evaluated: age >55 years, white blood cell count >16,000/mm³, blood glucose >200 mg/dL, serum AST >250 IU/L, and LDH >350 IU/L. Within the first 48 hours of hospitalization, an additional six parameters were assessed: hematocrit fall >10%, blood urea nitrogen (BUN) increase >5 mg/dL, serum calcium <8.0 mg/dL, arterial PO₂ <60 mmHg, base deficit >4 mEq/L, and estimated fluid sequestration >6 L. A Ranson score <3 was considered mild, whereas a score ≥3 was defined as severe disease.

C-reactive protein (CRP), albumin, red cell distribution width (RDW), and mean platelet volume (MPV). CRP and albumin levels were measured at the 48th hour following hospital admission, while RDW and MPV values were recorded at the time of initial admission. Previously established cut-off values from the literature were used: CRP >150 mg/L, albumin <4 g/dL, RDW >14.8%, and MPV >8.4 fL (14-16).

The primary outcome measure was the length of hospital stay. The relationship between laboratory parameters and hospitalization duration was analyzed.

All statistical analyses were performed using IBM SPSS Statistics for Windows, Version 22.0 (IBM Corp., Armonk, NY, USA). The normality of distribution was assessed using the Kolmogorov-Smirnov test. Continuous variables were expressed as mean±standard deviation or median (minimum–maximum), depending on distribution. Comparisons between groups were made using the Student's t-test or Mann-Whitney U test, as appropriate. Categorical variables were analyzed using the chi-square test. Correlations between laboratory parameters and hospital stay were evaluated using Spearman correlation analysis. A p-value of <0.05 was considered statistically significant.

RESULTS

A total of 164 patients diagnosed with acute pancreatitis were included in the study. The mean age was 58.4 ± 17.2 years, and 65.2% of the patients were female ($n=107$), while 34.8% were male ($n=57$). The most common etiology was biliary (68.3%, $n=112$), and 23.2% of the patients ($n=38$) had a Ranson score ≥ 3 , indicating severe disease. The mean length of hospital stay was 7.2 ± 5.5 days. Detailed demographic and clinical characteristics are presented in **Table 1**.

Table 1. Demographic and Clinical Characteristics of acute pancreatitis patients

Variable	Value
Age (mean \pm SD)	58.4 \pm 17.2
Sex	
Female	107 (65.2%)
Male	57 (34.8%)
Etiology	
Biliary	112 (68.3%)
Non-biliary	52 (31.7%)
Ranson score	
<3	126 (76.8%)
≥ 3	38 (23.2%)
Hospital stay (mean \pm SD)	7.2 \pm 5.5 days

When laboratory parameters were compared between patients with Ranson scores <3 and ≥ 3 , those in the higher score group had significantly elevated CRP levels (154.6 ± 103.9 vs. 61.15 ± 71.0 mg/L, $p < 0.001$) and a longer hospital stay (9.05 ± 6.5 vs. 6.65 ± 5.0 days, $p = 0.027$). However, no significant differences were observed in MPV, RDW, or albumin levels between the two groups ($p > 0.05$ for all). The comparative findings are summarized in **Table 2**.

Table 2. Comparison of Laboratory Parameters and Hospital Stay According to Disease Severity (Ranson Score)

Parameter	Ranson <3 (mean \pm SD)	Ranson ≥ 3 (mean \pm SD)	p value
CRP (mg/L)	61.15 \pm 71.0	154.6 \pm 103.9	<0.001
MPV (fL)	8.44 \pm 1.54	8.58 \pm 1.06	0.599
RDW (%)	14.17 \pm 2.08	14.44 \pm 2.15	0.493
Albumin (g/dL)	3.78 \pm 0.46	3.68 \pm 0.47	0.273
Hospital stay (days)	6.65 \pm 5.0	9.05 \pm 6.5	0.027

Further subgroup analyses were conducted using established clinical cut-off values. Patients with CRP >150 mg/L had significantly longer hospital stays compared to those with lower CRP levels (9.94 ± 7.85 vs. 6.55 ± 4.52 days, $p = 0.022$). A statistically significant difference was also observed in patients with MPV <7.5 fL, who had shorter hospitalizations than those with MPV ≥ 7.5 fL (4.85 ± 2.82 vs. 7.67 ± 5.75 days, $p = 0.020$). No significant differences in hospital stay duration were found based on RDW, albumin, or alternative MPV threshold values ($p > 0.05$ for all) (**Table 3**).

Table 3. Comparison of Hospital Stay According to Inflammatory and Clinical Parameters

Variable (Group)	n	Hospital stay Mean \pm SD (days)	p value
Ranson ≥ 3	38	9.05 \pm 6.54	0.027
Ranson <3	126	6.65 \pm 5.00	
CRP >150 mg/L	32	9.94 \pm 7.85	0.022
CRP ≤ 150 mg/L	132	6.55 \pm 4.52	
RDW >14.8	30	8.83 \pm 7.21	0.209
RDW ≤ 14.8	134	6.84 \pm 4.96	
MPV <7.5	27	4.85 \pm 2.82	0.020
MPV ≥ 7.5	137	7.67 \pm 5.75	
MPV <8.45	82	6.98 \pm 5.57	0.219
MPV ≥ 8.45	82	7.44 \pm 5.40	
Albumin <4 g/dL	116	7.59 \pm 6.05	0.664
Albumin ≥ 4 g/dL	48	6.27 \pm 3.62	

Spearman correlation analysis showed a moderate positive correlation between CRP levels and hospital stay duration ($r=0.458$, $p < 0.001$). No significant correlations were found between hospital stay and MPV, RDW, or albumin levels ($p > 0.05$ for all).

DISCUSSION

In this study, we evaluated the prognostic value of simple and accessible inflammatory markers—C-reactive protein (CRP), mean platelet volume (MPV), red cell distribution width (RDW), and serum albumin—in predicting disease severity and hospital stay in patients with acute pancreatitis. Our findings showed that both elevated CRP levels (>150 mg/L) and higher Ranson scores (≥ 3) were significantly associated with prolonged hospitalization. A moderate positive correlation was also observed between CRP levels and length of stay. Although MPV did not show a significant association at the conventional threshold (8.45 fL), a lower cut-off value (<7.5 fL) was associated with shorter hospital stay. In contrast, no significant relationship was found between RDW or albumin levels and hospital stay duration.

Acute pancreatitis is an inflammatory disease with a broad clinical spectrum, ranging from mild, self-limiting conditions to severe forms associated with necrosis, systemic inflammatory response syndrome (SIRS), and multiorgan failure. Early prediction of disease severity is essential for optimizing management and improving outcomes. Although scoring systems such as Ranson, APACHE II, and BISAP are widely used, they involve multiple parameters and may be impractical in time-sensitive clinical environments (1–3). The Ranson score, in particular, has been shown to correlate with both disease severity and length of hospital stay (3). In our study, patients with Ranson score ≥ 3 exhibited significantly longer hospital stays, consistent with its established prognostic utility.

Given the inflammatory pathophysiology of acute pancreatitis, laboratory parameters that reflect systemic inflammation are increasingly explored as prognostic tools. CRP, an acute-phase reactant synthesized by the liver in response to interleukin-6, is one of the most widely studied biomarkers in this context (6). CRP levels above 150 mg/L have been shown to be associated with pancreatic necrosis and poor outcomes (14). In our study, CRP >150 mg/L was significantly associated with longer hospital stay, and CRP levels showed a moderate positive correlation with hospitalization duration. This is in line with findings by Cardoso et al who reported that CRP measured within 48 hours could predict severe pancreatitis, pancreatic necrosis, and mortality (17). Similarly, Habib et al. observed that high CRP levels were strongly associated with necrotizing pancreatitis (14). Our results reinforce the prognostic utility of CRP and its role in early risk stratification.

The inflammatory process in acute pancreatitis includes cytokine release, endothelial activation, increased vascular permeability, and microcirculatory impairment. During this cascade, multiple inflammatory mediators such as TNF- α , IL-1 β , and IL-6 are rapidly activated, triggering hepatic production of CRP and other acute-phase proteins. These mediators not only drive systemic inflammation but may also contribute to organ dysfunction and tissue injury (18). CRP levels rapidly increase in response to these processes.

In contrast, MPV, which reflects platelet size and activity, showed a more complex pattern. Although no significant association was observed at the standard threshold (8.45 fL), a lower cut-off of <7.5 fL revealed a significant difference in hospitalization duration. This finding suggests a possible nonlinear relationship between MPV and clinical outcomes. MPV is known to be affected by thrombotic status and coexisting hematological conditions, potentially reducing its specificity in inflammatory settings (8). Notably, conflicting findings in the literature complicate interpretation; while Akbal et al. reported elevated MPV levels in acute pancreatitis associated with hypercoagulability, Beyazit et al. found significantly lower MPV in similar patients. These discrepancies may arise from variations in sample timing, disease stage, or technical differences in MPV measurement.

RDW, a marker of erythrocyte size variability, is influenced by oxidative stress, impaired erythropoiesis, and systemic inflammation. It has been reported as a prognostic indicator in cardiovascular and infectious diseases (9,19,20). However, in our study, neither RDW levels nor group comparisons based on the 14.8% threshold demonstrated significant associations with hospital stay or disease severity. This may be explained by the limited responsiveness of RDW in acute-phase conditions, as erythropoietic changes generally

require more prolonged inflammatory stimulation. Furthermore, RDW is influenced by numerous confounding factors such as iron deficiency, vitamin B12 or folate deficiency, chronic illness, and anemia, which may obscure its relationship with disease-specific inflammation in pancreatitis. Şenol et al. found that RDW could predict mortality in severe acute pancreatitis, but their population included a higher proportion of critically ill patients and used different inclusion thresholds (21).

Serum albumin, a negative acute-phase reactant, is influenced by hepatic function, nutritional status, and vascular leakage. Although Chen et al. showed that a significant drop in albumin within 24 hours of ICU admission was predictive of mortality in severe acute pancreatitis (22), our study found no significant relationship between admission albumin levels and hospital stay. One potential explanation is that albumin has a relatively long biological half-life (~21 days), which limits its responsiveness to acute inflammatory changes. Additionally, our use of a single time-point measurement on admission may not reflect dynamic changes in albumin during disease progression. Moreover, the relatively low rate of severe disease (only 23.2% had Ranson ≥ 3) could have reduced the likelihood of detecting significant associations.

This study has several limitations. First, it is a retrospective analysis conducted at a single center, which may limit the generalizability of the findings. Second, disease severity was evaluated solely based on hospital length of stay, rather than comprehensive clinical outcomes such as organ failure, ICU admission, or mortality. Finally, the interpretation of non-significant findings for RDW and albumin may be limited by the relatively small sample size and the absence of data on potential confounders such as nutritional status, anemia, and baseline comorbidities. Future prospective, multicenter studies with serial laboratory measurements and broader clinical endpoints are warranted to validate and expand upon our findings.

CONCLUSION

Taken together, our findings suggest that CRP and Ranson score remain reliable and practical indicators of disease severity and prognosis in acute pancreatitis. Although MPV demonstrated partial prognostic value depending on the selected cut-off, RDW and albumin were not significantly associated with outcomes in our study. These results support the integration of CRP into early risk stratification protocols, while also highlighting the need for larger, prospective studies to evaluate the full potential of MPV, RDW, and albumin as adjunctive prognostic tools.

ETHICAL DECLARATIONS

Ethics Committee Approval: Retrospective ethics committee approval is not required for articles generated from postgraduate/doctoral studies using research data prior to 2020 that were accepted for publication in the previous year but have not yet been published.

Informed Consent: Because the study was designed retrospectively, no written informed consent form was obtained from patients.

Referee Evaluation Process: Externally peer-reviewed.

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